

An Image of India: Reading Alka Saraogi's *Ek Break Ke Baad* (2008)

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Abstract:

The relationship between English and other Indian languages in India is a complicated one to begin with. In the post-colonial scenario, this complex relationship gets played out at various levels. This paper examines it in terms of fiction and the disparity between the representation of the contemporary Indian reality in Indian English fiction and fiction written in Indian languages. Taking the examples of *Ek Break ke Baad* by Alka Saraogi and *The White Tiger* by Aravind Adiga, both published in 2008 and using the politics of the Booker Prize as an outer political frame, one seeks to understand the various underpinnings of this complicated relationship.

Keywords: Post-colonialism, Indian novel, Indian Literature, Translation, Politics of representation and Visibility

The colonial experience has complicated the matrix of relationships between languages thriving or struggling to thrive in the so-called third world generally. In India, while passionate debates abound regarding the over-exclusive nature of the Eighth Schedule of the Constitution, one cannot deny the fact that there exists a decided superiority of English in every walk of life over the Bhasas. We all know that the equation between the Indian languages and English is definitely skewed as English continues to enjoy the status of master('s) language. It is the language of visibility and now in the age of sufficient Indianization of international prizes like the Booker, of veneration too.

We know it even better that English has assumed the role of the tongue that represents India to the rest of the world (especially the First World), that spawns pictures of India (whatever India really means in those contexts) for a hungry audience watching eagerly this economic juggernaut moving slowly but steadily on the wheels of an enormous demographic advantage. There is an obvious lack of parity in terms of availability of market, audience, translators, rewards and incentives between literature written in the Bhasas and in English in India. Also the perception that Indian literature can hardly match up to the writings in English in terms of maturity of experience, representation and thought, a perception that entirely stems out of ignorance has forced one to analyse two texts in this paper which look at contemporary India with all its conflicts and contradictions in very different ways. The politics of the Booker prize as far as representation from India is concerned, provides the outer frame to this comparative analysis. "Does the post-colonial exist only in English?" My answer would be no, it exists much

more in the Bhasas. I would go further and say that it even happens *to* them. The hierarchy that exists between the Indian languages and English is a product of this condition.

Alka Saraogi, an author who chooses to write in Hindi, has had a curious connection with the history of Booker prize vis-à-vis Indian authors. Her first novel, *Kalikatha: Via Bypass* (1997) came out five months after *The God of Small Things* (1997). There are curious similarities and parallels between the two novels. A comparative reading of those two novels leads to some easy and some very uneasy questions. How do two young Indian women writers arrive at the same questions of history and language at approximately the same time in their debut novels? To find an answer to that, it is necessary to go back to history. Later, in 2008, Saraogi wrote *Ek Break Ke Baad* which in its exploration of the theme and of narrative technique, can best be described as a novel with a difference. It concurrently tells the story of three men- KV Shankar Iyer, Delhi-based advertising Guru, ex-CEO of a leading advertising firm and an entrepreneur who at the age of 62 is still struggling to come to terms with his Brahminism that flows like blood in his veins. The second protagonist is Guru Charan, a high ranking executive in a leading MNC who vanishes from Delhi often and one gets to know much later that he is a wanderer, a philosopher and a spiritual Guru to many people like KV who seem to understand the reality but actually only partly. The third protagonist is Bhatt, a professional squirrel who hops from one job to another and is never satisfied because of his high sense of idealism in an age where ideals, values and morals seem to have become synonymous with money and power. Guru is the central protagonist who holds the loosely-knit narrative together. The novel is actually a series of comments on the contemporary metropolitan reality of India- a reality which is so full of conflict, so nebulous that it confuses the most analytical minds and at the same time, it is also a reality so concrete and in-your-face that a confrontation with it every moment of your conscious life is essential and inevitable. The novel consciously seeks to challenge the readers sense of complaisance about the world s/he lives in. Saraogi tells the reader through a conversation between Bhatt and Guru, "Why do you insist on seeing the sky from a single frame of your window? The sky is all around you. If you want to see the whole of it, you *have to* step out of that window!"¹ (Saraogi 111). The novel makes the reader think about the complexities not of a traditional society standing on the threshold of modernity but of one taking a deep plunge in the sea of globalization surrounding it and coming out wet and disheveled by the impact of the plunge. The rotten core defined here by caste, patriarchy and denial of those on the margins, surprisingly has remained intact. It has in fact adapted itself to the new ways of the world. But this is only one side of the story. The other side, which is not explored in Adiga's novel is that of the rise of the duplicitous and yet enabling sense of modernity. It is a trick but a trick which might be helping those on the margins. E.g. Bhatt starts selling tribal paintings from his father's traditional curio shop. He makes money out of it but so does the erstwhile hungry and famished indigenous artisan who is finally, only now, after selling his art, fed well. In all, this novel is a sophisticated exploration of India in a globalized world from the perspective of those dreamers who are not starving, not homeless, not naked, i.e. the rich.

Coming to the other end of the spectrum, Aravind Adiga's *White Tiger* explores the dreams of those who *are* homeless, starving, naked- the poorest of the poor. Adiga presumes

a lot here. While Saraogi takes great pains in describing to her Hindi readers terms like outsourcing, carbon credit and BPO, Adiga breezes past these bewildering ideas and focuses primarily on the narrative of Balram Halwai. So which author out of the two is being more presumptuous? Saraogi? Because she feels that *her* reader would not know? Or Adiga who feels that *his* reader knows? We are talking about two different languages, two different types of readers and two different worldviews! Adiga's novel went on to become hugely successful. In it we witness Balram, the erstwhile subaltern not just speaking but speaking the language of power in India. Furthermore, the reader witnesses this ex-subaltern speaking to the Prime Minister of China and by default becomes equivalent to Hu as s/he is taking a voyeuristic peek into the letters meant for Hu. The speech of the subaltern here is fraught with complications. The thin line between Balram's object position and agency is slimmed down further by his metamorphosis into a successful entrepreneur. The impossible metamorphosis of the protagonist propelled by the wings of hatred and anger (arising out of constant class and caste discrimination Balram receives from his master's family) and a heinous crime seems to project an anomaly, a case extraordinaire which cannot be a defining picture of India in twenty-first century. And yet the book's roaring success suggests that the world would want to class India in this very slot: hungry for change, full of potential, ready to do anything for success. Full of sharp turns and a racy narrative, this novel is a far cry from the somber, deep meditation on the idea that India is, in *Ek Break ke Baad*. We definitely need to ask why two novels written in the same year and around the same theme of contemporary Indian economy and its impact on the traditional society are received so differently. The deeper and more disturbing question is why the one out of these two that presents an easy, monolithic picture of India goes on to become the master narrative of this emerging international power.

If we move on to more recent times and view the success of Geetanjali Shree's *Tomb of Sand* (2021) another facet of this issue emerges: Shree benefitted immensely from the fact that this novel had a western translator. Daisy Rockwell's act of translation became the bridge between this novel and the rest of the world and the reason behind the International Booker Prize. The voice in the west which introduces and perseveres: like Yates to Tagore, is still a prerequisite more than hundred years later, for Indian literature to compete and succeed.

To conclude, one may take into account the reader's response to the representation of the post-colonial reality in these novels. One cannot help but ponder on the myriad markers of this reality encountered frequently in Saraogi's writings. There is a suggestion that the post-colonial consciousness cannot be ignored, neither can one escape it. In our day-to-day lives we do not think of ourselves as consequences of history. But what is identity without history? In *Koi Baat Nahin* (2004), Shashank is at times shaken out of his deep reverie to the misty dusk in the Victoria Memorial park by the shrill whistle of the guard indicating the time of closing of the park. Saraogi's novels shake the reader out of her/his complaisant attitude towards routine realities in a similar way. One finds oneself in a misty dusk where things look unclear and yet clear. The answers to questions related to the post-colonial condition whether related to the languages or the content of our representations, though not straight or monolithic, may a-maze us. However, one needs to seek them all the time if change is desired.

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